

Fig. 1 3N Sulphuric acid

Fig. 2 6N Sulphuric acid

Fig. 3 3N Sulphuric acid

Fig. 4 5N Sulphuric acid

Inflexions corresponding to R_1, R_2, R_5, R_6, R_7 and R_8 have been observed but those corresponding to R_3 and R_7 last over many days. That for R_8 is permanent as expected. This means that there are only small periods of induction for further oxidation after R_1, R_2 and R_5 , perhaps none after R_2 and R_4 and quite long ones after R_6 and R_7 .

The stable products have been identified chemically and spectrophotometrically. R_1, R_2, R_5 and R_7 correspond to formation of free radicals whose presence at these stages has been verified by induced polymerization of acrylonitrile to which the reagents were added in the right proportion at the right time.

In the reduction of acid dichromate by the diol again the indications are that Cr(VI) (P) gains electrons in steps of one in the following sequence

Inflexions corresponding to the first three have been observed of which the P_2 stage lasts for many hours and P_3 is permanent. There is no observable reduction to Cr(II) (P_4), but a trace may perhaps be formed on prolonged storage with excess diol in 6N sulphuric acid to suppress the inflexion for Cr(III). These results show that at any stage in these reactions quite a number of oxidizing and reducing particles are involved. This situation has been ignored by some earlier workers^{3,4} who have followed the reactions kinetically.

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References

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